

SPORT YO`NALISHI TALABALARI UCHUN INGLIZ TILINI O`QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada nofilologik oliy ta'lim muassasalarida, xususan sport yo'nalishidagi talabalarga ingliz tilini samarali o'qitish masalalari yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda talabalar chet tilini nafaqat til sifatida, balki kasbiy faoliyatda qo'llaniladigan vosita sifatida o'zlashtirishlari uchun yaratiladigan o'quv muhiti va qo'llaniladigan metodik yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqilgan. Jumladan, CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) metodi asosida ishlab chiqilgan dars mashg'ulotlari, o'qish va matnni tushunish bo'yicha zamonaviy texnologiyalar (pre-reading, while-reading, post-reading, klaster, savol-javob, skimming, scanning)ning qo'llanishi tahlil qilingan. Maqolada sportga oid "Attack techniques" (hujum texnikasi) mavzusidagi matn asosida mashqlar ishlab chiqilgan hamda talabalar bilan interaktiv faoliyatlar o'tkazilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: CLIL, ingliz tili, sport, o'qitish metodikasi, hujum texnikasi, pre-reading, post-reading, skimming, scanning, klaster texnologiyasi, ingliz tili va kasbiy tayyorgarlik.

Chet tilini o'qitishning muvaffaqiyati va samaradorligi ko'p jihatdan til o'rganilayotgan mamlakatdagi darslarning tuzilishi va tashkil etilishiga bog'liq. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarning yoshi, o'quv bosqichida qo'yilgan maqsadlar, o'quv mazmuni, hamda psixologik va pedagogik omillar ham muhim rol o'ynaydi. No-filologik oliy ta'lim muassasalarida chet tilini o'qitishning tabiati, asosan, bu tilni o'rgatishning boshlang'ich bosqichi qanday tashkil etilganiga bog'liq bo'ladi.[1] Oxir-oqibat, maqsad — talabalar ingliz tilini shunchaki til sifatida emas, balki akademik va professional muvaffaqiyatga erishish vositasi sifatida o'zlashtiriladigan muhit yaratishdir. No-filologik sohalarda yuzaga keladigan o'ziga xos qiyinchiliklarni hisobga olgan holda, moslashtirilgan strategiyalarni qo'llash orqali o'qituvchilar ingliz tilini o'qitish samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshirishlari va talabalarni kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyatlariga yaxshiroq tayyorlashlari mumkin.[2,3]

Quyida sport yo'nalishi talabalari ingliz tilida uchun ishlab chiqilgan mutaxassislikka oid mashqlarni o'qish va ularni tushunganligini turli zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali tekshirib ko'rdik. O'quv qo'llanmada har bir unit o'qish, gapirish, eshitish, yozish bilan birga leksik va grammatik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan.

Attack techniques (hujum texnikasi)

Attack techniques (hujum texnikasi) consist of actions performed with or without the ball. These include standing position, sliding, and jumping as the first group; and passing, extending, hitting the ball, and deceptive movements (fint) as the second group.

Standing Position- tik turgandagi holat. To perform the technical method well, the player should assume a more advantageous position called a "ready position." If the attack action requires an upright posture, the defense position is slightly more bent forward.

Sliding-sirpanish. On the court, sliding is performed through walking, running, and jumping. Volleyball players slightly lean their upper bodies forward while on the court, bending their legs slightly and sliding on their toes. To reach the ball quickly, short runs of 3–5 meters

are necessary. During the execution of an attack shot, sliding towards the ball and quick jumping help ensure accuracy and speed.

Jumping-sakrash. Jumping is performed from a stationary position or after running, with one foot used as a spring. For an attack shot, the jump is made with the feet parallel at a distance of 20–30 cm apart. In this position, the body leans forward, the arms swing upward, and the player jumps. One foot is used as a spring, utilizing the force from the entire body (see Figure 1).

Sport yo`nalishi ham nofilologik bo`lganligi uchun talabalar matni to`g`ridan -to`g`ri tushunishga qiynaladi, qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf qilish uchun CLIL metodidan bosqichma-bosqich foydalandik. Ya`ni matni tushunishga 1.(pre-reading) tayyorgarlik ko`rildi. Savol-javob o`tkazildi “Do you know any attack techniques in volleyball?” “Have you ever tried jumping or sliding on the court?”

Kalit so`zlar bilan ishlash: “Match the word with the picture” (standing position, sliding, jumping). So`zlar tarjimai (Inglizcha–O`zbekcha kartochkalar bilan). 2.While-Reading (Matni tushunish va tahlil qilish). Skimming – Matnning umumiy mazmunini tezda tushunish uchun o`qish (ko`z yugurtirish). Scanning – Matndan aniq ma`lumot (raqam, ism, sana) izlab o`qish texnologiyalaridan foydalanildi. “Attack techniques” matnida berilgan ma`lumotlari talabalar eslab qolganligi va o`rganganligini klaster texnologiyasi orqali tekshirdik

3.Post-readingda gaplarni o`qish va ularning To`g`ri (True) yoki Noto`g`ri (False) ekanligini aniqlash kerak. Noto`g`ri gaplarni to`g`rilash aytilgan

1. The "ready position" requires players to always stand upright, regardless of the situation.

2. Sliding is performed by walking, running, or jumping with the upper body slightly leaned forward.

3. Players should perform short runs of 3–5 meters during sliding to quickly reach the ball.

4. Jumping for an attack shot is only performed from a stationary position.

5. When jumping for an attack, the feet should be parallel and placed 20–30 cm apart.

6. The use of both feet as a spring is crucial for an effective jump.

Task 3. Translate these collocations and match definitions (Quyidagi soʻz birikmalarini tarjima qiling va taʼriflar bilan moslang.) Attack techniques, Standing position, Ready position, Upright posture, Defense position, Sliding on their toes, Short runs, Attack shot, Quick jumping, Feet parallel

Descriptions:

- A. A method used to prepare for an attack or defense.
- B. A key action performed to execute an accurate and strong hit.
- C. Moving efficiently with the toes slightly gliding on the court surface.
- D. A preparatory stance with knees bent and body slightly leaning forward.
- E. Keeping the body straight, often necessary for attack actions.
- F. Movements over 3–5 meters to quickly reach the ball.
- G. Body alignment where both feet are at an equal distance apart.
- H. A defensive position requiring a forward-leaning stance.
- I. Strategies or actions performed with or without the ball to gain an advantage.
- J. Fast vertical movement to reach or hit the ball effectively.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni koʻrsatadiki, sport yoʻnalishi talabalari uchun ingliz tilidagi kasbiy matnlarni oʻzlashtirishda CLIL metodidan foydalanish ijobiy samara beradi. Bosqichma-bosqich yondashuv orqali talabalar nafaqat oʻquv matnini chuqur tushunishga erishadilar, balki kasbiy sohada ingliz tilida fikr yuritish, terminologiyani oʻzlashtirish hamda kommunikativ koʻnikmalarni rivojlantirish imkoniga ega boʻladilar. Bu yondashuv ularning kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyatida xorijiy tilni samarali qoʻllashlariga asos yaratadi.

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